

SOME WAYS OF TEACHING PHRASAL VERBS

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Abstract: This article discusses the challenges and importance of learning phrasal verbs for learners of English as a second language. Because of the vitality of phrasal verbs to native speakers of English, ESL/EFL students should be taught and educated to be capable of understanding and using phrasal verbs when interacting in English because knowledge of phrasal verbs would normally lead to better English language proficiency and more native-like communication. For this reason, some ways and activities are recommended below which can be useful in teaching and learning process of phrasal verbs efficiently.

Key words: English, phrasal verbs, games and activities, bingo, charades.

Phrasal verbs present a difficult challenge for most students who study English as a second language. Generally, nine out of ten ESL students will tell you the hardest English vocabulary to learn are phrasal verbs, those sneaky little verbs that mean one thing when paired with one preposition and a completely different thing when paired with another. And since it's so hard for students to learn them effectively on their own, it's up to teachers to help them. Unfortunately, there is no quick formula for students to learn and understand them. There is no one rule for determining which preposition to use after the verb. Each phrase has to be learned and understood individually.

So what is the best way for students to learn phrasal verbs? First, students should understand that phrasal verbs cannot be accurately translated because of their idiomatic nature and the fact that they are compound phrases. Phrasal verbs sound quite strange to non-native speakers of English. However, once the student can understand the nature of phrasal verbs, they do not usually have a problem using them.

As always, having the students do a fun activity is the best way to teach English. It is advisable to use following games and activities in teaching phrasal verbs.

Bingo:

Making bingo cards with the phrasal verbs on them is a great idea. You can play this game by calling out the synonym for the phrasal verb (you call out "return" while the students have "come back" on their cards.) You can also act out the phrasal verb instead of calling out the synonym. You can do a variation on the Taboo game: for "wake up" you might say, "first thing in the morning." You can do all of them combined, especially when the phrasal verbs are a mix of verbs with some that can be acted out and some that can't.

Stories:

Any narrative that students can follow really helps them understand phrasal verbs in the context of real life. You could teach a whole lesson plan based on the following text, and then have the students write their own story on a particular topic based. The chosen topic can be like "my weekend" or "my friend's birthday party" etc. In this way, Students' narrative skills are also improved.

Charades:

This activity works well with phrasal verbs in addition, can also be incorporated into many other classroom lessons. This game demands one player acting out or miming the meaning of a word so that the other players have to guess the word. This activity is recommended to be done after the students have already been presented the phrasal verb vocabulary of the day.

Put the students into small groups and give each group pieces of paper or index cards with a different phrasal verb on each one. Then one student takes the first card and acts out the word while the students in the group try to guess what the word is. Before starting the game, model the exercise in front of the groups by doing it yourself. Say "what word?" and then act out an easy one, like "to wake up" until

someone guesses it. Then show them the cards and pass them out. You can then go to each group and show them individually how to proceed, having one student in each group start, telling them to take turns.

Taboo:

This is a game where one person tries to convey what the word is without saying any of the words itself. This game is better than charades when the meaning of the phrasal verbs are not physical actions, like to make up (your mind). Start the game the same way as with charades, with small groups and the words on pieces of paper. Again, model the activity in front of the group before having the groups do it themselves.

Act it out or Draw it:

This game gives students practice with phrasal verbs for movement. Cards are placed in two piles — one pile for one-pointers, and another pile for two-pointers. Students are placed in two teams. One player on each team starts by choosing a phrasal verb (from either pile) and trying to get their team members to guess the phrasal verb by either drawing it, acting it out, or a combination of the two. Once the phrasal verb is guessed, another member of the team chooses a card and does the same. The team with the most correct guesses after 15 minutes is the winner.

Catapult: For the Digital Classroom

If you have iPads in your classroom or use the computer as part of your teaching style, then this online game, Catapult, is a great tool for teaching phrasal verbs. The game is ideally used as a friendly competition-style game, but it can also be played by just one person or team.

The game is played as follows: A sentence is presented with a missing portion of a phrasal verb. Students must read the sentence and choose from three options to fill in the blank. The graphics place the team in two towers, and their phrasal verb skills will help them catapult the other team out of its tower.

We enjoy this game because it's simple to understand and play, making it perfect for short periods of time. This game is great if you have five or ten minutes left over at the end of class and need a time-filler. Just split your class into two teams, and have them line up down the center of the classroom. Give each classroom a sign or baton to use as a "buzzer," and have two students face off for every question.

To sum up, English as a second/foreign language teachers should highlight, to their students, the importance of using phrasal verbs and the significance of recognizing their meanings. Likewise, teachers should be familiar with commonly-used phrasal verbs and teach them, in order to help and make it easier for their students. Teaching phrasal verbs should be taken into serious concern in English second/foreign language teaching classrooms and materials, which should include phrasal verbs as a part of vocabulary, listening and speaking drills and classroom exercises. Learning English language like a native, requires that students of English as a second/foreign language and non-native English language learners, practice using English phrasal verbs and become more knowledgeable about the meaning of, at least, the most common-used phrasal verbs. The more, the better the important thing is not to overwhelm yourself and your students with an endless list of phrasal verbs but instead, set realistic goals. It's impossible to take in the meaning of all of them at once, as there are thousands!

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